

MODEL BASED ASSESSMENT OF URANIUM MIGRATION IN THE REGION OF VULCHE DERE CREEK, DOWNSTREAM OF “ELESHNITSA” TAILINGS POND, SW BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT: Uranium mining activities in the region of Eleshnitsa uranium deposit (SW Bulgaria) were carried out in the period of 1955–1992. For the purposes of the milling plant near the mine, a tailings pond was exploited since 1969. Its construction took place by blocking the natural depression of the Vulche dere creek (in the catchment area of Mesta River) by an earth-fill dam. Currently, the pond contains about 9 million tons of hydrometallurgical wastes, including approximately 730 tons of uranium. The present study considers the process of infiltration of uranium from surface water in depth in the Quaternary sediments at the valley of the creek, downstream of the tailings pond. For this purpose a modeling was performed using HYDRUS-1D software, estimating the variations of uranium concentration in the soil profile for the period 1966–2016. Additionally a simulation was done for prediction of the concentrations in the future.

Key words: uranium, Eleshnitsa, HYDRUS-1D, simulation studies

INTRODUCTION

Uranium mining activities in the region of Eleshnitsa uranium deposit (SW Bulgaria) were carried out in the period of 1955–1992. It is located in the molasse sediments of Oligocene age that are produced by the erosion of the Rila and Pirin mountain ranges (figure 1). The mine was called “Druzhba” and the ore was extracted mostly through heap leaching at the surface, but in-situ leaching also occurred on at least two occasions. At the end of the 1960s, the “Zvezda” milling plant was built near the mine and for its purposes a tailings pond was exploited since 1969. Its construction took place by blocking the natural depression of the Vulche dere creek (in the catchment area of Mesta River) by an earth-fill dam (figure 1). Currently, the height of the dam is 74 m, and the surface area of the tailing pond is 250 000 m². The pond contains about 9 million tons of hydrometallurgical wastes, including approximately 730 tons of uranium (Skenderov *et al.* 2000).

Figure 1. Location of Eleshnitsa uranium mine and a view from the tailings pond dam to the valley of the Vulche dere creek

In the period 2003–2005, the tailings pond was recultivated under an EU-sponsored rehabilitation project (PHARE BG 9904-03-01-02) and a purification station was constructed to treat the drainage water. After purification the water is discharged into Vulche Dere creek, which in turn flows into the Mesta River. Additionally, in 2002, two piezometers were constructed at the valley of the creek – one among Quaternary sediments, with depth of 20 m (piezometer B3-25) and the other one (piezometer B3-26) with depth of 135 m – in Neogene. The studies performed in 2012–2016 confirm the presence of hydraulic and chemical interaction between the surface water of Vulche dere creek and the groundwater in the Quaternary aquifer

(Kolev 2016, 2017). There is no any influence on the surface water of Mesta River and the groundwater in the Neogene aquifer (Kolev *et al.* 2014). The present study considers the process of infiltration of uranium from surface water in depth in the Quaternary sediments at the valley of the creek.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

HYDRUS-1D code

Simulation vertical profile model was performed using HYDRUS-1D software, estimating the amount of uranium reaching the bottom of the Quaternary sediments and its concentrations in the soil profile at different time periods. The program HYDRUS-1D numerically resolves the advection-dispersion equation on the basis of the solution of the partial differential equation of Richards, which describes the water flow in a variably saturated porous medium, or so-called hydraulic model (Šimůnek *et al.* 2008). Richards' equation is often comprehensively represented by means of the van Genuchten-Mualem model. Resolving this equation requires the knowledge of two nonlinear functions, namely the soil water retention function and the hydraulic conductivity function (van Genuchten 1980). Hence, the following so-called hydraulic parameters which describe those characteristic functions need to be known: residual (θ_r , L³ L⁻³) and saturated water content (θ_s , L³ L⁻³); α [L⁻¹] and n [-], which are empirical constants defining the shape of the curves; and saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_s , L T⁻¹). The hydraulic parameters were determined for the soil samples on the base of pedotransfer function analyses using the ROSETTA (Schaap & Leij 1998; Schaap *et al.* 1998, 2001) program incorporated in the HYDRUS-1D. To characterize the interaction between uranium and soil, or so-called mass transfer model, the distribution coefficient (K_d) is used in the predictive analyzes and, respectively, in the convective-dispersion equations included in HYDRUS-1D.

Modeling schematization

A vertical profile model was implemented with depth of 20 m. The schematization is in accordance with the field observations, the archive data of geophysical surveys, the results from the grain-size distribution analyses and the uranium decay constant is also taken into account. The upper boundary condition was set as specified pressure head (corresponding to the water level of the creek), and the lower boundary condition was set as free drainage. The total time for the simulations was set to 50 years, with the uranium intake set at the top of the profile, with varying concentrations consistent with those actually measured in the 1966-2016 monitoring observations of surface water of Vulche dere creek. The partition coefficient K_d used to predict the interaction between radionuclide and soil (Vandenhove *et al.* 2009) was calculated from LHyGeS (Laboratories of HYdrology and GEochemistry of Strasbourg) laboratory data (Van Meir 2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of modeling, performed using the HYDRUS-1D software, are presented as a change over time of uranium concentrations in the soil profile for four observation moments – in 1979, 1991, 2003 and 2016 (figure 2).

Figure 2. Variations of uranium concentration in the soil profile for the period 1966–2016

Comparison of the concentration obtained at the end of the model period at the bottom of the quaternary horizon (0.09 mg/l at 20 m depth) (figure 3) with the actual concentration measured in piezometer B3-25, whose depth is also 20 m (0.12 mg/l) shows that the compiled model describes relatively accurately the behavior of uranium in time and space. On figure 3 there are also visible fluctuations in the concentrations of uranium which were actually observed in the piezometer during monitoring in the period 2005-2008.

Figure 3. Bottom concentrations of uranium for the period 1966–2016

Additionally a simulation was done for prediction of the concentrations distribution in the soil profile in the future. Consideration of two prediction scenarios – one with set seasonal variations in uranium concentrations in Vulche dere creek and one with set constant mean concentration (figure 4), shows how strongly the effect of these seasonal fluctuations influences on the distribution of uranium concentrations in the soil profile. In the first case, an extremely dynamic picture is observed due to the entry of different amounts of uranium over relatively short periods, while in the second case, its concentration equalizes over the entire depth of the profile in a period of less than 3 years.

Figure 4. Predicted concentrations of uranium in the soil profile: a. Given seasonal changes in concentrations in the Vulche dere creek; b. Given a constant mean value of the concentration in Vulche dere creek (the curves for the four observation moments coincide here)

Given the extremely strong dependence on fluctuations in the concentrations of the pollutant in the surface creek water, it is difficult to make a long-term prediction of the water status in the quaternary aquifer. However, the well-functioning of the compiled model allows accurate prediction of the distribution of uranium concentrations in the soil profile, when introducing new data from the ongoing monitoring of the surface water of Vulche dere creek.

CONCLUSION

Based on field investigations, archive data and laboratory analyses, numerical models were performed using the software program HYDRUS-1D and all the models had minimal relative errors in the water mass balance of the entire flow domain. The model of the migration of uranium from the surface water of Vulche dere creek in depth into the quaternary horizon, describes relatively precisely the behavior of uranium in time and space. The prediction scenarios examined show a strong dependence of the distribution of uranium concentrations in depth on the fluctuations of concentrations in the Vulche dere creek. Although it is difficult to draw a long-term prediction for the groundwater status in the quaternary aquifer, the well-functioning of the model allows correct prediction of the distribution of uranium concentrations in the soil profile, when introducing new data from the ongoing monitoring of the surface water of Vulche dere creek.

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